

Rodent pests of upland and lowland rice at a derived savanna site in Nigeria

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Rodents are one of the major pests damaging the rice crop in Nigeria. Their population, damage, and species variation were monitored in upland, rainfed, and irrigated lowland areas in the 1994-95 dry and wet seasons. These fields were located at different sites within the experimental farm at IITA, Ibadan. The location represents a derived savanna agroecological zone, with an average bimodal rainfall of 1,400 mm.

Rodent species were sampled by mechanical trapping, fecal droppings, and use of poisoned baits for identification. Damage was monitored at various growth stages of the crop. The total of all catches was used to calculate percentage of occurrence of individual species. Varietal preferences based on damage in different replicates were monitored in breeders' trials. Zinc phosphide was first administered followed by coumatetralyl (0.375 ai) rodenticide to capture and manage the rodent population.

Ten rodent species were trapped (see table). In the uplands, three species—*Arvicantis niloticus rufinus* (Nile rat), *Rattus morio* (jumping mouse), and a lagormorph *Xerus erythropus* (ground squirrel)—were observed in the wet season. Three other species—*Dasymsus incomtus* (shaggy rat), *Mastomys natalensis* (multimammate rat), and *Steatomys caurinus* (fat mouse)—were observed in the irrigated lowlands in both dry and wet seasons. All three species dig burrows in levees around fields.

Rodent species and crop damage stage in different rice-growing environments.

Common name	Scientific name	Rice-growing environment and season ^a	Occurrence (%)	Crop damage stage	Months of damage
Ground squirrel	<i>Xerus erythropus</i>	U; WS	3.3	Tillering	May to Aug
Nile rat	<i>Arvicantis niloticus rufinus</i>	U; WS	17.3	Maturity	Sep to Oct
Jumping mouse	<i>Rattus morio</i>	U; WS	2.5	Maturity	Sep to Oct
Fat mouse	<i>Steatomys caurinus</i>	I; DS	5.3	Maturity	Apr to Aug
Shaggy rat	<i>Dasymsus incomtus</i>	I; DS	14.0	Maturity	Jun
Multimammate rat	<i>Mastomys natalensis</i>	I; DS	35.8	Maturity	Jun
Swamp rat	<i>Malacomys longipes</i>	I, R; WS, DS	3.5 5.1	Maturity	Mar to Oct
Black rat	<i>Rattus rattus frugivorus</i>	I, R; WS, DS	0.3 0.5	Maturity	Mar to Oct
Slender gerbil	<i>Taterillus gracilis</i>	R; WS	6.6	Maturity	Oct to Dec
Cane rat	<i>Thryonomys swinderianus</i>	U, R, I; WS	2.3 1.5 2.0	Vegetative to maturity	May to Dec

^aU = uplands, I = irrigated lowlands, R = rainfed lowlands, DS = dry season, WS = wet season.

Two other species, *Malacomys longipes* (swamp rat) and *Rattus rattus frugivorus* (black rat), overlap in both rainfed and irrigated lowlands. One species, *Taterillus gracilis* (slender gerbil), was observed in rainfed lowland fields only. Another large-sized species, *Thryonomys swinderianus* (cane rat), was observed in all three rice-growing ecologies and at all crop growth stages. In irrigated lowlands, it invades only during crop maturation, when fields are dry. The table shows crop damage stage and frequency of occurrence of each rodent pest. The multimammate rat occurred in the highest frequency (36%).

Rodent activities were mostly nocturnal but, at high population density, they were also seen during daytime. Only the ground squirrel was diurnal. All rat species, except for the cane rat, cut individual tillers at maturity. The cane rat damaged all tillers in a hill before proceeding to

other hills. It also did not accept any poisoned or unpoisoned bait and therefore was controlled by wire fencing. Among the rice varieties tested, DJ11-307-15 was selectively attacked by the cane rat in the rainfed lowland yield trial in all three replications. The cane rat may have certain preference traits compared with other rodents. Many other rice varieties were attacked in one or two replications. ■

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.